

Study on Health Status and Prevalence of Anxiety Among Doctors in a Tertiary Care Centre

Rijhwani Puneet¹, Kalra Vidita², Parakh Rishabh³, Shah Sarthak⁴, Sarna Mukesh Kumar⁵, Kalra Rajendra⁶, Kalra Anju⁷, Setia Mansi⁸, Kumar Chitresh⁹, Verma Suchita¹⁰, Tyagi Ambika¹¹, Aneja Mahima¹², Khadadiya Mitul¹³, Chaudhary Rini¹⁴, Chaudhary Arushi¹⁵

¹Head of Department, Dept. of General Medicine, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Hospital, Jaipur, Rajasthan

^{2,3,4, 8,9, 10, 12, 13, 14,15} Resident, Dept. of General Medicine, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Hospital, Jaipur, Rajasthan

⁵Professor and Unit Head, Dept. of General Medicine, Mahatma Gandhi College and Hospital, Jaipur, Rajasthan

⁶Senior Consultant, Orthopaedic Surgeon, Kalra Clinic, Delhi

⁷Senior Consultant, Pediatrics, Kalra Clinic, Delhi

¹¹Assistant Professor, Dept. of General Medicine, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Hospital, Jaipur, Rajasthan

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Vidita Kalra

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Abstract:

Background: Doctors deal with human life and saves patient's live and in doing so the tough Combined with this working environment and lifestyle related factors affect the mental health of doctors. So this study tries to measure the anxiety level of doctors and assess the factors affecting the health status of doctors.

Material and Methods: A cross sectional observational study was done among the Consultants and Post graduate residents of Mahatma Gandhi Medical College & Hospital Jaipur. Demographic, health related factors, work related factors etc were noted and anxiety level was measured using HAM-A scale.

Results: The mean HAM-A score of the study subject was 5.89 (SD 7.85). Anxiety is more prevalent in residents though not clinically significant. Significant anxiety was present in female and unmarried doctor ($p < 0.05$). More duty hours, more number of night duties and higher work pressure were mainly responsible for higher anxiety among residents ($p < 0.05$). Moreover and taking outside meal, taking meal when they get time and doing less exercise were mainly responsible for higher BMI among doctors.

Conclusion: Work related factors as duty hour, number of night duties, life style related factors as outside meal, irregular meals, less exercise affect physical health and mental health of doctors.

Keywords: Mental Health, Health Status, Anxiety, Working environment, BMI.

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Introduction

To be a medical professional is a great privilege that is looked upon with respect and interlaced with humility, as doctors have been bestowed the noble responsibility of looking after patients. Dealing with situations where human lives are at stake involves persistent work pressure and stress which affects the mental health of the doctors. This stress elevates the possibility of doctors suffering various health problems. Doctors or residents work for about 60-70 hours per week—and sometimes more—and this means that they often have no (or very less) time to deal with their personal problems. The life expectancy of doctors is 59 years as compared to 67.9 years of an average person in

India.[1] According to Indian Medical Association's research, deskbound job and inactive lifestyle, lack of exercise, stress and obesity are primary instigators of heart diseases in the medical fraternity. Although the risk of heart diseases increases with age, doctors avoid having a regular medical checkup and tend to rely on self-diagnosis and treatment. The 10-year-long study conducted by the Indian Medical Association for Kerala found that 27% of the doctors had died due to heart diseases, 25% due to cancer, 2% by infection, and 1% by committing suicide. The respondents mentioned stress as the major contributor of early deaths, followed by lack of periodic health checkups. [2]

Even it is well expected that health of a physicians directly impacts the health of the larger population, as numerous studies have established a link between the health behaviors of physicians and their interactions with patients. [3] So this study aimed to study the health status and prevalence of anxiety among doctors in a tertiary care centre.

Methodology

A cross-sectional observational study was done among all the Consultants and Post graduate residents of Mahatma Gandhi Medical College Hospital Jaipur. included all consultants and residents of pre-clinical, para clinical and clinical branches and those who are pregnant and not willing to give consent were excluded.

Due ethical clearance was taken from institutional ethical committee. After taking due consent socio-demographic, detail about co-morbidities were noted. Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale (HAM-A) [4] was used to measure the level of anxiety among study subjects. The scale consists of 14 items to measure psychic and somatic anxiety.

Each item is scored on a scale of 0 (not present) to 4 (severe). Data compiled in MS Excel and analysis was done in SPSS version 16 and results were described using Chi square test and considered significant if p value found to be less than 0.05.

Results

The mean age of study subject was 37.87 yrs with SD 10.59. There were 104 (69.3%) males and 46 (30.7%) females and the male to female ratio was 2.26. It includes 36 (24%) unmarried doctors and 114 (76) married doctors. In this study there were 50 (33.3%) consultants and 100 (66.7%) residents, out of which 30 (20%) belonged to pre-clinical subjects, 30(20% belonged to para- clinical subjects and rest 90 (60%) belonged to clinical subjects.

On studying the co-morbidity, we found that 20(14.2%), 65(46.1%), 13(9.2%), 33(23.4), 5(3.5%) and 5(3.5%) doctors were suffering from diabetes, dyslipidemia, joint pain, hypertension, COPD and CAD respectively. Doctors on normal BMI includes 54 (36%), 68 (45.3%) were pre obese and rest 28 (18.7%) were obese. The mean BMI was 26.78 Kg/sqm (SD 3.54).

Table 1: Distribution of study subject according to HAM A scale (N=150)

Variable	Frequency	Percent	Mean (SD)
No Anxiety	80	53.3	5.89 (7.85)
Mild Anxiety	49	32.7	
Mild to Moderate Anxiety	18	12.0	
Moderate to Severe Anxiety	3	2.0	
Total	150	100.0	

As shown in the table 80 (53.3%) were not suffering from any anxiety and 49 (32.7%), 18 (12.0%), 3 (2.0%) were suffering from mild anxiety (<17), mild to moderate anxiety (18-24) and moderate to severe anxiety (25-30) respectively. The mean HAM-A score of the study subject was 5.89 (SD 7.85).

Figure 1: Bar diagram showing distribution according to HAM A Scale

Table 2: HAM-A Score according to Designation and Subject (N=150)

Variable	No Anxiety	Mild Anxiety	Mild to Moderate Anxiety	Moderate to Severe Anxiety	Total	P
Designation						
Consultant	30 (60.0%)	15 (30.0%)	4 (8.0%)	1 (2.0%)	50 (100.0%)	0.672
Resident	50 (50.0%)	34 (34.0%)	14 (14.0%)	2 (2.0%)	100 (100%)	
Total	80 (53.3%)	49 (32.7%)	18 (12.0%)	3 (2.0%)	150 (100.0%)	

As described in the table among consultants 30 (60%) were not suffering from any anxiety and rest 15 (30%), 4 (8%) and 1 (2%) were suffering from mild anxiety, mild to moderate anxiety and moderate to severe anxiety respectively. Among residents 50 (50%) were not suffering from any anxiety and rest 34 (34%), 14 (14%), and 2 (2%) were suffering from mild anxiety, mild to moderate anxiety and moderate to severe anxiety respectively and this

difference of various grades of anxiety was not statistically significant (p=0.672).

On comparing the HAM- A score among consultant and resident by doing one way ANOVA we found the difference of prevalence of anxiety among consultants and residents was not statistically significant (p>0.05) i.e anxiety more in resident but not significant.

Figure 2: Cluster Bar Diagram showing HAM-A Score according to Designation

The mean HAM-A score among male doctor was 7.10 (SD 3.9) and among female was 9.07 (SD 5.5) and this difference was statistically significant. (p=0.013). HAM-A score among unmarried was 11.56 (SD 5.1) and among married it was 6.48 (SD 3.5) and this difference was statistically significant. (p=0.000).

Table 3: Relationship between Designation Vs Work and Lifestyle Related Factors related factors

Variable		Consultant	Resident	Total	p
Duty Hour	<48Hr	50(100.0%)	48 (48.0%)	98 (65.3%)	<0.001
	48 to 72	0, (0.0%)	41 (41.0%)	41 (27.3%)	
	>72	0 (0.0%)	11(11.0%)	11 (7.3%)	
Number Of Night	0	10 (20%)	20 (20%)	30(20%)	<0.001
	1-4	48 (80.0%)	48 (48.0%)	88 (58.7%)	
	>4	0 (0.0%)	32 (32.0%)	32 (21.3%)	
Feeling Work Pres-	No	32 (64.0%)	42 (42.0%)	74 (49.3%)	<0.05
	Yes	18 (36.0%)	58 (58.0%)	76 (50.7%)	

sure					
Getting Time to Relax	No	18 (36.0%)	55 (55.0%)	73 (48.7%)	<0.05
	Yes	32 (64.0%)	45 (45.0%)	77 (51.3%)	
Have Outside Meals	Never	13(26.0%)	12(12.0%)	25(16.7%)	<0.05
	Once A Week	16(32.0%)	54(54.0%)	70(46.7%)	
	Twice A Week	11(22.0%)	18(18.0%)	29(19.3%)	
	Thrice or More A Week	10(20.0%)	8(8.0%)	18(12.0%)	
	Everyday	0(0.0%)	8(8.0%)	8(5.3%)	
Fixed Mealtime	Yes	36(72.0%)	25(25.0%)	61(40.7%)	<0.001
	When Get Time	14(28.0%)	75(75.0%)	89(59.3%)	
Exercise Duration Per Week	No Exercise	11(22.0%)	32(32.0%)	43(28.7%)	<0.001
	< 30 min	7(14.0%)	28(28.0%)	35(23.3%)	
	>30 to <90 min	18(36.0%)	12(12.0%)	30(20.0%)	
	>90 to <150 min	0(0.0%)	27(27.0%)	27(18.0%)	
	> 150 min	14(28.0%)	1(1.0%)	15(10.0%)	
Total		50 (100%)	100(100%)	150 (100%)	

As shown in the table all the consultants had duty hour less than 48 hour. Among residents 48(48%), 41(41%) and 11(11%) had duty hour less than 48 hr, 48 to 72 hr and more than 72 hr respectively and this difference was statistically significant ($p=0.000$) with residents have more duty hours compared to consultants. Similarly, among consultants 10 (20%) had no night duty, 48(80%) had 1-to-4-night duties and rest had no night duty. Among residents 20(20%) had no night duty, 48(48%) had 1-to-4-night duties and 32 (32%) had >4-night duties per month and this difference was statistically significant ($p=0.000$) with residents have more night duties per month. In this study among consultant 18 (36%) feel work pressure and among residents 58(58%) feel work pressure and rest didn't feel so and this difference was also statistically significant ($p=0.011$). Again, among consultant 32 (64%) and among residents 45 (45%) were getting time to relax and rest were not getting time to relax, and this difference was statistically significant. ($p=0.028$).

In this study 13(26.0%), 16(32.0%), 11(22.0%) and 10(20.0%) consultants never take outside meals, have outside meal once a week, have twice a week and have outside meal thrice or more a week respectively. Similarly, 12(12.0%), 54(54.0%), 18(18.0%), 8(8.0%) and 8(8.0%) residents' consultants never take outside meals, have outside meal once a week, have twice a week, have thrice or more a week and have outside meal everyday respectively. This difference was statistically significant ($p=0.004$). Again 36(72.0%) consultants had fixed mealtime and 14 (28%) had meal when they get time. Similarly, 25(25%) residents had fixed mealtime and 75 (75%) had their meal when they get time. This difference was statistically significant ($p=0.000$). In this study 11(22.0%) consultants did not exercise and rest 7(14.0%), 18(36.0%), 0(0.0%) and 14(28.0%) consultants

exercise <30 minutes, >30 to < 90 minutes, >90 to <150 minutes and > 150 minutes respectively. Again 32(32.0%) residents do not exercise and rest 28(28.0%), 12(12.0%), 27(27.0%) and 1(1.0%) resident exercise <30 minutes, >30 to < 90 minutes, >90 to <150 minutes and > 150 minutes respectively and this difference was statistically significant ($p=0.000$).

Discussion

Medical profession though being a high esteemed and noble profession is filled with responsibility of caring after the sick and debilitated patients. This profession unlike other profession is directly dealing with the human life and so utmost care need to be taken while taking care of patients. All this along with long duty hours, lack of rest, work pressure not only affect the physical health but also affect the mental health of the doctors. That is why the life expectancy of doctors is less compared to general population in India.[1] According to cardiologist Dr. K. K. Aggarwal, physicians are more vulnerable to heart disease, diabetes, and even paralysis as a result of stress.[5] Keeping all these things in mind this study was planned.

In this study 80 (53.3%) were not suffering from any anxiety and 49 (32.7%), 18 (12.0%), 3 (2.0%) were suffering from mild anxiety (<17), mild to moderate anxiety (18-24) and moderate to severe anxiety (25-30) respectively. The mean HAM-A score of the study subject was 5.89 (SD 7.85). Among consultants 30 (60%) were not suffering from any anxiety and rest 15 (30%), 4 (8%) and 1 (2%) were suffering from mild anxiety, mild to moderate anxiety and moderate to severe anxiety respectively. Among residents 50 (50%) were not suffering from any anxiety and rest 34 (34%), 14 (14%), and 2 (2%) were suffering from mild anxiety, mild to moderate anxiety and moderate to severe anxiety respectively and this difference was

not significant ($p=0.672$) which means anxiety was more in resident but not significant. Many studies were done to find out the prevalence of depression and anxiety among doctors. As per study done by Parikh et al [6] among resident doctors of general hospital in Ahmedabad it was found that about 36.6% had anxiety and anxiety severity was higher. Another study by Dave et al [7] on 520 resident doctors find out that about 36.6% doctors had anxiety. Erica Frank et al [8] studied health practices of Canadian physician and found out that 5% reported poor physical or mental health. So overall anxiety was found prevalent among doctors in most of the studies.

The mean HAM-A score among male doctor was 7.10 (SD 3.9) and among female was 9.07 (SD 5.5) and this difference was statistically significant ($p<0.05$). HAM-A score among unmarried was 11.56 (SD 5.1) and among married it was 6.48 (SD 3.5) and this difference was statistically significant ($p<0.001$). So female and unmarried had more anxiety.

Similar finding was there in a study by Atif et al [9] who found that impact of gender on anxiety scores was significant ($p=0.002$). 9(17.31%) males and 24 (53.33%) females had mild to moderate anxiety while 4(7.69%) males and 3(6.66%) females had severe anxiety. But there was no significant impact of marital status($p=0.157$) on anxiety scores. Parikh et al [10] did not found any association of sex and marital status with stress levels among resident doctor

All the consultants in our study had duty hour less than 48 hour. Among residents 48(48%), 41(41%) and 11(11%) had duty hour less than 48 hr, 48 to 72 hr and more than 72 hr respectively and this difference was statistically significant ($p=0.000$) with residents have more duty hours compared to consultants. Similarly, among consultants 10 (20%) had no night duty, 48(80%) had 1-to-4-night duties and rest had no night duty.

Among residents 20(20%) had no night duty, 48(48%) had 1-to-4-night duties and 32 (32%) had >4-night duties per month and this difference was statistically significant ($p=0.000$) with residents have more night duties per month. In this study among consultant 18 (36%) feel work pressure and among residents 58(58%) feel work pressure and rest didn't feel so and this difference was also statistically significant ($p=0.011$). Again, among consultant 32 (64%) and among residents 45 (45%) were getting time to relax and rest were not getting time to relax, and this difference was statistically significant. ($p=0.028$).

On doing one way analysis of variance (one way ANOVA) between HAM-A score and duty hour per week, number of night duties per week, feeling work pressure and getting time to relax it was

found that the difference was statistically significant ($p<0.05$). So, in this study residents have more duty hours and night duties compared to consultants and feeling more work pressure and not getting time to relax compared to consultants. Other studies also find out more or less similar relationship. Parikh et al [6] found out that anxiety was significantly higher among residents working more than 12 h a day compared to those with less working hours ($P = 0.00$). Eva Niewiadomska et al [11] reported the occurrence of anxiety symptoms (as per HADS) by 181 (25.8%) doctors. Dave et al [7] found that anxiety was significantly higher among residents working more than 12 h a day compared to those with less working hours ($P = 0.00$), and also in those who considered their department environment strict compared to ones who considered it lenient or were neutral ($P = 0.003$). But Khaula Atif et al [9] in a study at Combined Military Hospital, Lahore found no significant impact of working hours per week($p=0.338$), additional duties($p=0.444$), on anxiety scores.

In this study 13(26.0%), 16(32.0%), 11(22.0%) and 10(20.0%) consultants never take outside meals, have once a week, have twice a week and have outside meal thrice or more a week respectively. Similarly, 12(12.0%), 54(54.0%), 18(18.0%), 8(8.0%) and 8(8.0%) residents consultants never take outside meals, have once a week, have twice a week, have thrice or more a week and have outside meal everyday respectively. This difference was statistically significant ($p=0.004$). So, residents take more outside meals and that may be due to more duty hours, more work pressure and hostel life.

In this study 36(72.0%) consultants had fixed mealtime and 14 (28%) had meal when they get time. Similarly, 25(25%) residents had fixed mealtime and 75 (75%) had their meal when they get time. This difference was statistically significant ($p=0.000$). So, residents are not taking their meal on time, and they are taking meal when they get time which may impact their physical health.

In this study 54 (36%) doctors had normal BMI, 68 (45.3%) were pre obese and 28 (18.7%) were obese with mean BMI 26.78 Kg/sqm (SD 3.54) In this study 11(22.0%) consultants did not exercise and rest 7(14.0%), 18(36.0%), 0(0.0%) and 14(28.0%) consultants exercise <30 minutes, >30 to < 90 minutes, >90 to <150 minutes and > 150 minutes respectively. Again 32(32.0%) residents do not exercise and rest 28(28.0%), 12(12.0%), 27(27.0%) and 1(1.0%) resident exercise <30 minutes, >30 to < 90 minutes, >90 to <150 minutes and > 150 minutes respectively and this difference was statistically significant ($p=0.000$). So, residents are doing either no exercise or doing exercise for lesser duration compared to consultants. This may affect the health of residents.

Kiran Prakash K et al [12] found that prevalence of physical inactivity among physician was 60.1%. About 36.1% were moderately active, while few (3.5%) of the subjects were involved in vigorous exercise in their leisure time. Tonima Sultana et al [13] found that, 3.0% doctors were involved in vigorous-intensity activities and more than 30% were involved in moderate-intensity activities. In general, low physical activity was prevalent in 39.9% of the participants. They found about one third (33.9%) of the participants were overweight, and 10.9% were obese. Erica Frank et al [8] it was found that physician respondents exercised an average of 4.7 hours per week, including mild exercise. Prakash K et al [12] found out that more than half of the subjects in each category of educational qualification were found to be overweight ($p>0.05$)

Nutrition survey on healthcare workers by Wei Chen [14] in China in June 2020 showed that limited access to home-cooked, irregular eating behavior, short mealtime and a sedentary lifestyle with daily exercise deficiency had unfavorable impact on the health condition, with development of overweight or obesity in 32%. Cross-sectional survey of 328 NHS doctors working in two NHS Trusts done by James Winston et al [15] 70% ($n = 229/328$) of doctors reported using their hospital canteen each week, with on average 2.07 (SD 2.09) visits per week on average. In this study 20(14.2%), 65(46.1%), 13(9.2%), 33(23.4), 5(3.5%) and 5(3.5%) of the doctors were suffering from diabetes, dyslipidemia, joint pain, hypertension, COPD and CAD respectively. So most common prevalent disease in our study was dyslipidemia which 46.1% (65) of the doctors are suffering. Again on analyzing the prevalence in consultants and residents it was found out that 15 (20.0%), 29 (38.7%), 11 (14.7%), 18 (24.0%), 15 (6.7%) and 5 (6.7%) consultants and 5(6.7%), 36 (48.0%), 2 (2.7%), 15 (20.0%), 0(0.0%) and 0 (0.0%) residents were suffering from diabetes, dyslipidemia, joint pain, hypertension, COPD and CAD respectively. Ramesh Venkatesh et al [16] studied the prevalence of back pain in ophthalmologist and found that self-reported prevalence of back pain was 70.5%.

Fully 49% of respondents had low back pain, followed by neck pain (33%) and upper extremity symptoms (16%). Eva Niewiadomska et al [11] found that the chronic diseases affected 480 (68.5%) of the surveyed doctors out of which obesity (68.3%) was the most prevalent followed by hypertension (33.8%), dyslipidemia (27.1%), allergy (26.7%), CAD (24.4%), diabetes (14.1%) respectively. Wei Chen [14] in their survey found that the frequently reported chronic diseases comprised dyslipidemia (21.50%), cardiovascular diseases (8.42%), cancer (5.87%), and diabetes (2.49%) among health care worker.

Conclusion

Anxiety is more prevalent in residents though not clinically significant. One of the reasons for this difference may be duty hour and number of night duties as duty hours and even number of night duties were considerably high among residents compared to consultants. Residents significantly feel higher work pressure and do not get time to relax in comparison to counterpart the reason may be duty hour and number of night duties and the tough level of medical course. Significant anxiety was present in female and unmarried doctor. Most of the doctors take outside meal once a week and take meal when they get time. Taking meal when getting time is significantly higher among residents. Majority of doctors didn't do any exercise. Eating outside meal is significantly higher among residents. Not doing exercise and taking frequent outside meal may be associated with major pre obese BMI of the doctors and thus affect the physical health of doctors.

So, work environment related factors, meal related factors, lifestyle related factors affect affecting the physical and mental health of doctors. So government should take suitable steps such as to improve the work environment by providing sufficient number of doctors in the ward; taking care of mental health by starting courses of medication, yoga, sports etc and providing healthy food in the hospital so that physical and mental health of doctors can be improved.

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